

Removing the Obstacles to Network Technology Adoption

Hanafy Meleis

National Institute of Standards and Technology, Advanced Technology Program

Abstract

The obstacles to adopting new network technologies that enable new applications and services are reviewed and discussed. Technologies such as client-server and interconnection mechanisms enable the realization of new applications which are "nice to have." Making these new technologies as easy as possible to exploit and use is a key in adopting them. Obstacles such as cost and complexity of managing the changes have been proven to be two of the barriers to adopting these technologies. Additionally, ignoring the importance of the legacy systems and their associated applications, services, and infrastructures as well as introducing a set of new technologies which may not work well with the older systems impedes the acceptance of these new technologies. A set of migration technologies and strategies must be developed to remove the obstacles and to accelerate the adoption of these new network technologies.

1. Introduction

There are continuous developments in the technology of connecting computers together to share resources and information, and to enable collaborative and distributed applications. Both the physical connectivity and the software built on top of it have seen many new developments in recent years. Yet often, these new technologies are only adopted slowly and reluctantly, despite the advantages they seem to offer. In contrast, developments in other areas of the computing technology seem to be received much more enthusiastically.

It is not necessary to look very far to identify some of the networking developments that have not achieved the success they apparently deserved. The networking protocol suite X.25, which seemed to offer enormous promise when it first appeared in the late 1970's, only

exists in a few niches. More recently the Fiber Distributed Data Interface (FDDI), which seemed a natural successor to Ethernet, has had only limited success. At higher levels, one can point to the Open Systems Interconnection (OSI) protocol, which after years of development and thousands of staff-years of effort, seems to have made a marginal difference in the marketplace. Each of these examples has its own reasons for failure, but a common denominator between all is the slow development of the technology in spite of the needed features by the users.

On the other hand, some interconnection technologies have been readily accepted and are now in widespread use. An example is Ethernet, which is now almost a universal means for connecting workstations and personal computers. Another is the Internet Protocol, which is already widely used in the academic and scientific community and is fast becoming part of everyday business practice in the commercial sector as well. It is instructive to compare the successes and the failures of these technologies and to determine the differences that have affected their destinies.

The present time is particularly exciting for networking, with the U.S. Government's initiative around the "Information Superhighway," and the emergence of ATM as the wide-area networking technology achieving the speed and bandwidth needed for real-time multimedia transmission, including video, voice and data. Yet what is to stop these new technologies from suffering the same fate encountered by some of their predecessors? In this paper the focus is on the network technology, specifically on interconnection technology. A similar discussion can apply to some other areas of technology such as large main-frame applications.

It is well known that nobody will invest in a technology for its own sake. There has to be some business reasons that make it attractive. The phrase "business need" appears often in this context, but for a new networking technology that is leading the market, this is not really appropriate. In its early days one can

only hope that the technology is “nice to have” by offering an attractive alternative solution to some problem. This means that it must be relatively easy and inexpensive to exploit; otherwise, it will be simpler to carry on doing things the old way. Only when there is truly a “need” will expensive and complex solutions be acceptable. This is shown, for example, by today's large mission-critical wide-area networks, such as those used by banks and airlines.

The lack of enthusiasm in adopting network technology, such as FDDI, contrasts with other new technologies. In personal computing, for example, every new device or stand-alone application quickly finds its mark. The major difference is that in networking, each system (whether hardware, software, transmission, or management) has to function as an integral part of a large and complex system. This complex system is itself often operating at the limit of the complexity that its owners and operators are willing or able to deal with. Adding yet another unknown, which may cause a large impact on the overall system and lead to new types of problems in the existing network, makes the risk of adoption too high for something which is “nice to have.” The contrast with the PC environment can be clearly illustrated by the fast rate of adoption of CD-ROM drives. Even though, currently, the majority of users have no true “need” for these devices, the latter's reasonable cost and ease of installation have led to their adoption at an astonishing rate; they are now sold with 25% of new systems, as well as being used as upgrades to existing systems.

In section 2 we examine some of the new directions in system design, networking technology, and applications. Distributed computing has led to the adoption of client-server systems. New high-speed networking technology such as ATM has enabled new applications such as multimedia. Some of these applications are making the technology “nice to have” and will be briefly discussed in section 3. In section 4, we identify and discuss obstacles to adopting new networking technologies.

2. Technology Directions

2.1 The Impact of Client-Server Computing

In the client-server computing model, the traditional monolithic application is divided into two, or sometimes three, parts: the *client*, where the user interaction takes place, and the *server*, where the intelligence of the application is usually held. A third level provides a

broker between the client and server, allowing clients to be independent of any particular server, and making it easy for them to take services from several servers at once.

One of the key virtues of this approach is that it allows the features of different applications to be combined in novel ways at relatively little cost. Whereas modifying traditional applications, or even worse, trying to integrate them, is a software development nightmare, the client-server approach allows this integration to take place only at the client, leaving each application on the server as “the” application in the traditional way. New user interfaces can combine these functions and make their independent existence transparent to the human user. Wrapper techniques can be used to integrate existing monolithic applications into the client-server environment, by converting the typical screen and keyboard interface into something that resembles a remote procedure call. Applications newly developed in the client-server model offer a natural modularity and can readily be used as building blocks to construct composite applications.

Another advantage of this approach is its natural scalability. A great deal of computing power is associated with the user interface and with data manipulations that can readily be colocated with it. Since each additional user implies an additional client, and hence additional computing power, the system naturally grows with the number of users. Data can often be partitioned onto different servers, with transaction processing techniques ensuring consistency across the multiple databases. While some centralization must remain around the kernels of data which must be kept together, its isolation from other processing tasks means that it presents much less of an overall bottleneck than in traditional “mainframe” computing styles.

Taking an existing “mainframe” application and converting it to use a client-server approach will not necessarily have much effect on network traffic. It may even reduce it, since there is no longer any need to send screenfuls of text and graphics across the network. It does, however, open the door to true wide-area distributed computing, in which significant volumes of data have to be moved between servers as well as to the clients.

Figure 1 shows the evolution of the client-server technology. At the left, applications are served on centralized systems with traditional terminals accessing them. In the center, client systems (personal computer [PC] or workstation [WS]) have replaced terminals and front-end processors provide data sharing among the clients but the applications remain relatively centralized.

This is the typical situation today, where legacy systems are still very much a part of reality. Finally, at the right is an advanced client-server system, where the applications are themselves distributed.

Effective deployment of advanced client-server solutions implies the existence of a distributed systems infrastructure, providing services such as naming and broker services. The breadth of services to be provided will grow slowly over time to include more sophisticated services such as security.

2.2 Networking Technology

The biggest single impetus to computer networking was the development of the Ethernet, not only as a successful technology but as a widely-available, reliable and inexpensive family of products. The Ethernet increased commonplace network performance by a very significant factor; even today it provides adequate speed for the great majority of networked computer users.

Figure 1. The Development of Client-Server Computing.

In wide-area networking, available performance is currently much more constrained. T1 lines operating at 1.5 Mbit/sec are readily available, at least in the United States, but because they provide only a point-to-point service, their use for data requires the construction of a private data network with its inherent complexity and cost of management (both perceived and real). Broader wide-area networking is still constrained by the technology of analog modems. Although this technology continues to make astonishing progress, it will never provide speeds in excess of a few tens of kilobits/second.

The basic ISDN technology, providing 64 Kbit/sec or 128 Kbit/sec, is increasingly available but has become

viewed as a niche and unable of providing dramatic improvement.

The first of the new generation of high-speed networks was FDDI. FDDI has been viewed mainly as a "better Ethernet," providing 100 Mbit/sec. Up until now, its deployment has been mainly limited to large installations and to those with specialized requirements to move huge volumes of data (such as high-energy physics). FDDI, like Ethernet, is essentially a Local Area Network technology, although it is in fact possible to deploy FDDI over distances of tens of kilometers.

The most exciting new development in the networking technology has been the introduction of ATM. This is a true wide-area technology, developed by

the telephone industry to serve all of its future needs. It provides connection at speeds of 155 Mbit/second and higher, and can carry effectively traffic that requires constant-speed (isochronous) delivery, such as voice and real-time video, as well as traditional computer data. For "traditional" networked computing, ATM offers for the first time LAN bandwidth in the wide-area environment, freeing the application designer from the need to treat the local and wide area situations differently.

Back in the LAN domain, another important direction is the tendency of LANs towards offering dedicated bandwidth to individual users ("personal Ethernet"). The original goal of Ethernet was to provide a high bandwidth that everyone would share. The development of the hub with twisted pair wiring as the norm for network installation, in conjunction with FDDI or ATM backbones, allows each user to actually receive all of this bandwidth. This is important when considering multi-media traffic to the desktop.

2.3 The Impact of Multi-Media

A consequence of applying computer technology in other domains is that everything has become "just bits": voice on the telephone, hi-fi music, and now video as well. Once something is reduced to bits then it can all be processed in the same way. In particular, the techniques for sending information across a digital network are the same regardless of how the data will be presented to a human user (whether as letters on a character-cell terminal or as a program on a TV set). (There are special requirements in real-time applications, such as television, but these can be incorporated into a general-purpose network and do not require a completely parallel infrastructure.)

Simply digitizing video generates vast amounts of data, beyond the capacity even of ATM. By the nature of video there is an enormous amount of redundancy in this data, and a variety of compression techniques have been developed to reduce the bandwidth to something that can reasonably be dealt with. In the extreme, the needs of video-conferencing can be dealt with by just two 64 Kbit/sec channels (one in each direction). VCR-quality video can be reduced to around 2 Mbit/sec. Chips to decompress video in real-time are available now, while real-time compression is just becoming possible (and is already commonplace at the level required for videoconferencing).

At these bandwidths, video can easily be moved over data-type networks. ATM, in particular, contains features to support real-time video, such as isochronous transmission. Further technology developments allow

the necessary bit rates to be delivered over telephone wiring, or to be multiplexed in large quantities over traditional cable TV lines. In parallel, disk storage has evolved to the point where it is economically reasonable to use disks to store hundreds of movies in compressed digital form. All of this leads to a new video delivery concept called Interactive Video Services, where video is piped to the user's home or desk and is under his or her control. The possibilities that this offers are further described below.

3. Making the Technology "Nice to Have"

This section identifies some application areas which will create a demand for high-performance networking. Investment in these areas, and the delivery of attractive products, will stimulate user investment in networking technology.

3.1 Consumer Video Services

The technology for Video-on-Demand and Interactive Television has an obvious application in providing video services to the home. As a first step, it allows the domestic VCR to be replaced, giving the equivalent service but with the pictures (and sound) being delivered over cable TV or telephone wiring. In itself this offers advantages over the existing VCR/video store situation. The most obvious is that the user can choose from his or her armchair, without having to visit the video store. Since there is no limit to the number of times the same material can be concurrently transmitted, there is no risk that the desired movie will be unavailable, and because a single distribution center can serve a much larger number of people than a single store, it can afford to hold more specialized material. It can also provide on-demand viewing of material which the video store cannot handle, such as today's news or sports events.

Beyond Video-on-Demand is Interactive Television. The commonly cited example is tele-shopping, where the users guide the material being shown according to their particular tastes. The same technology can also allow games to be played over the network rather than from CD-ROMs at home, again permitting a wider choice and making it possible to pay on a usage basis.

3.2 Business Video

The same technology has applications in the business environment. For example, it can be used to

provide training at the desk, or for the distribution of news and talks. Typically, the distribution in this case would be over intra-building wiring such as FDDI or ATM, rather than over cable or telephone wiring.

3.3 Telecollaboration

The term telecollaboration means the use of information and communications technology to make easier the problems of working together over long distances. Sometimes telecollaboration is done in the context of making an existing work-at-a-distance function better, while at other times it is done in the context of creating new opportunities for doing so (such as working from home). The most obvious application in this field is videoconferencing. Although this has a high profile, in reality most person-to-person business communication can be handled as effectively using the normal telephone and it will take a relatively long time before the habit of seeing the person at the other end of the line becomes commonplace.

Probably of more short-term use are tools which permit genuine shared working in a distributed environment. "Whiteboard" type tools, for example, allow sketches and transparencies to be shared and to be under the complete control of the current speaker. In terms of practical utility this is more important than video-conferencing, but once it is in use it will stimulate a desire to see what the other person or people are doing.

There are many opportunities to enhance the efficiency of geographically-separated groups by taking advantage of the information-sharing capabilities now available. Often, these opportunities depend closely on the job being undertaken and cannot be addressed by "generic" software. One example is the distribution for review of "rushes" (animations, titling, etc.) in the production of finished video material. Networking and video techniques can now replace video cassettes and courier services. Another example is the remote viewing of X-rays and other medical images, allowing specialist attention to a patient without the patient having to travel to the specialist. These are niche applications, which will often be developed by small companies having a deep understanding of their target market.

4. Removing the Obstacles

If it is truly essential to the business of an organization to install some new technology, then a way will be found no matter how difficult the installation may be. But to expand the market, we need to make the

technology attractive even if the application is merely "useful." (As an analogy, consider the success of the CD player. People bought them because "it seemed like a good idea," they were affordable, and installing them and getting them to work was easy. If the installation had required professional help, only a small number of users with a genuine need would have had it installed, even if the device cost was low.) Applications like desktop telecollaboration, for example, will only become indispensable when they are already in widespread use. To get them to that point, they must be made appealing and practical. If they are difficult to install and get working, they will end up as "shelfware."

In the following section, we identify the obstacles to the widespread use of high-speed networking, and the investments that are necessary to overcome them.

4.1 Cost

New technologies are generally more expensive to provide than whatever existing solution they replace. This is almost inevitable because they are initially used in low volume. There are no manufacturing economies of scale, and the development costs have not been amortized. It is normal that the provider of a service charges more to reflect the increased cost. Yet this is the very time when, because of the risk and change associated with using the new technology, users are generally not prepared to pay a premium price. A kind of deadly embrace can ensue, in which the lack of user adoption means that the economies of scale do not happen, and the price premium remains. This phenomenon occurred both with X.25 and with ISDN. In both cases, the extra cost was not outweighed by the perceived benefit and they have both, so far, remained confined to specialized use rather than to widespread, general-purpose use hoped for by their initiators.

In contrast to this has been the experience with the Minitel in France. The Minitel provides a universally-available text terminal service which can be used to access a huge variety of information sources. Although by today's standards somewhat old-fashioned, it is very widely used. Its success is due to the fact that France Telecom initially made the terminal equipment available free of charge, and the service available purely on a usage basis (and free for its initially intended use, Directory Enquiries). This subsidy, during the adoption phase, avoids the stagnation which has afflicted ISDN and X.25.

4.2 Configuration and Management

Network equipment is traditionally complex to install, configure and maintain. There are necessarily many components involved, and when a problem occurs, it requires a combination of knowledge, experience, and good tools to locate the problem and correct it. New technology is at an obvious disadvantage here, because there is no experience either in the technology itself or in how it interacts with existing network components. In addition, the tools, which often develop in a rather ad hoc fashion, may not be as good as tools for established technologies.

Some aspects of this problem can be tackled in a direct way. For example, a new technology can be delivered with tools that integrate well with management tools in common use. This is becoming easier now that the protocols and management platforms for networking are becoming de facto standards.

A more general solution, though, depends on being able to limit the risk to existing operations when new technology is introduced. We refer to this as *decoupling*. For example, suppose that a high-speed WAN link is to be introduced in order to support a video conferencing trial. To the end-user, this new application must appear integrated with the existing infrastructure. For example, voice-links and electronic mail are to be used in close conjunction with the new facility. Taking a long-term perspective, it would be natural to incorporate the new link into the existing network, making it available for other classes of traffic. For the network manager,

though, this means potentially destabilizing the entire network, which may be critical to the business (and certainly to the network manager's job!) for the sake of the new application. For something which is "nice to have," this is likely to prove unacceptable. Therefore, if the application is to be adopted on a trial basis, it must be possible to use the necessary new network facility in parallel. This amounts to setting up a small parallel network. There are network architectures which make this difficult, but the product itself (the combination of the application and the networking technology) must be designed in such a way that this is possible. For example, a video conferencing application could use private LAN protocols coupled with dedicated LAN servers, rather than being integrated into the normal LAN protocols and routers.

This approach does introduce a further complication of its own, though. Suppose that the trial is successful, and that after several pilots it is decided to undertake a full-scale implementation. At this point the cost of the new network facilities is likely to become an issue, and there may well be a desire to start integrating them fully into the infrastructure, particularly since the experience and tools will now have developed to a point where this may be deemed relatively low risk. If the decoupling approach initially adopted makes it hard to move now to a fully integrated approach, then this will in turn become an obstacle. Therefore, the technique used to permit decoupling in the early days must also allow for progressive integration later on.

Figure 2. Decoupling.

Figure 2 illustrates this aspect of decoupling, using a simplified form of the well-known layered model of network architecture. Figure 2(a) shows the initial situation. In Figure 2(b), we see the new network technology applied in parallel, minimizing the risk to the existing applications. In Figure 2(c), we see the desirable long-term state, where the new technology has been fully integrated and can be used by all applications.

Another approach to decoupling is to make the new technology *transparent*, that is, to make it invisible to the existing infrastructure. This can be done, for example, by providing an interface that makes it look like something which is already in use. For example, an ATM link could be provided with a physical interface that emulates an existing synchronous link operating at a lower speed. Figure 3 shows this technique.

Problems in the operation of the new technology manifest themselves in the same way as problems with the existing technology. Diagnosis of the problem may require an understanding of the new facility, but interactions between the old and the new are avoided. Even better, the two can exist in parallel, so that a disabling problem with the new facility can be patched around using the old one. This technique is applicable to

software technologies as well as to hardware. For example, a new naming service could be given programming and management interfaces that are compatible with its predecessor.

A limitation of this technique is that it is often impossible to make the new technology appear *completely* identical with the old. Unintended and unforeseen differences may impact the existing network in unexpected ways, resulting in problems that are still hard to track down. For example, an ATM network may introduce a transit delay variance which does not exist with a synchronous service. This might impact network protocols in a way which has never been seen before, leading to difficult problem diagnosis and consequent disenchantment with the new ATM service even though the real fault lies in the old technology.

Whatever techniques are used, the new technology will not succeed if the network manager who has to deal with it is not comfortable with it. During the introductory phase even minor problems may lead him or her to distrust it, particularly if they have wider ramifications. The form in which the new technology is presented needs to take this into account.

Figure 3. Decoupling by making the new technology transparent.

4.3 Avoiding Unnecessary New Technology

For the technologist, it may seem attractive to combine new technologies. A new management capability, for example, may seem to simplify the use of a new physical interconnect, and it would seem logical to introduce them both at once. For the user, however, this means dealing with multiple unknowns at once. The perception of risk and insecurity will be correspondingly greater, and will act as a disincentive to adoption.

It is much better for the new technology to be usable on its own, with only minimum adaptation of the environment in which it operates, even if this results in some short-term inelegance in the deployment. This is no doubt a factor in the poor take-up of the OSI protocols. They were designed to work together as a suite, and no account was taken of the possible need to operate with other protocols already in use. Indeed, this was a conscious decision, since it was intended that OSI should make all such protocols obsolete. A user who

wanted access to the X.400 mail protocol, for example, also had to have the OSI lower layer protocols in use for interconnection purposes. The recent success of some of the OSI application protocols (such as X.400 for mail and X.500 for naming) owes a great deal to the development, outside the formal standards bodies, of techniques for allowing their use over non-OSI network infrastructures.

4.4 Packaging

New services need to be packaged in such a way that it is easy to identify and obtain exactly what is required to take advantage of a new application in conjunction with the network technology. Examples of this are often seen in the world of personal computing. Modems, for example, are typically sold in a package which also includes usable communications and fax software. No additional purchase is required in order to use the modem for the purpose for which it was most likely bought.

For more sophisticated applications and services, this is no doubt harder to achieve. For example, telecollaboration may require equipment associated with the workstation hardware (camera and video board), network adapters, and high-speed interconnect. Nevertheless, adoption will be quicker if some packaging can be devised which will meet the needs of a significant proportion of potential users, taking into account the equipment which is in common use.

4.5 Application Development and Integration Tools

To take full advantage of a new application will typically require that it be integrated with some existing application. For example, effective telecollaboration requires access to all the user's files from the application that provides it. If this kind of integration is not made easy, then the new application becomes in effect marginal, and will not be integrated into the user's work operation. Today, various techniques exist whereby an application (in the traditional sense) can appear as an element in a more elaborate application which is built to suit a particular business's needs. Fourth Generation Languages and, in the PC environment, the Visual Basic programming language, need to be accommodated by applications.

Another aspect of application integration is the need to accommodate *legacy applications*. These applications are typically not designed to be integrated in this way. They have a view of themselves as "top of the heap" and

do not provide open interfaces. Legacy integration tools make this possible, by emulating a human user and transforming the resulting interactions into an Application Programming Interface which can then be accessed from the new application. Combining this with the use of rapid development systems such as Visual Basic means that existing applications can readily become part of new applications that include multimedia, for example.

5. Conclusion

Network technology has many unique aspects which hinder its adoption, no matter what apparent advantages are offered. The failure of promising new facilities to achieve their potential is relatively common. The provider of a new capability (whether a service offering, a hardware, or a software product) must do all that is possible to overcome the intrinsic obstacles, otherwise see his new technology join the pile of those that did not make it. Of particular importance is the need to *decouple* the new offer from impact on the existing network infrastructure, and from other new technologies which may be linked to it. It must also be recognized that a technology on its own is of no use. Applications must be provided which can be directly understood by the user, and of which the new technology forms an indispensable part.

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